

Early populations of the Yucatan Peninsula

also known as “La Señora de Las Palmas”

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Entry tags: Archaeological Site, Religious Group, Cemetery, Language, Unknown, Religious Place, Early populations of Mexico, Submerged caves in Quintana Roo

The cenotes and caves of Tulum, Quintana Roo, are repositories of an important archaeological and paleontological heritage that accounts for the history from the shallow seas that formed the calcareous substrate of the Yucatan Peninsula to the Pleistocene prairies, the animals that inhabited there and the first human groups of Asian origin. 13,000 years ago this region was very different from what we know today: the sea level was 65 meters below the current level and the caves, in which we can dive today, were completely dry. The Tulum region was inhabited by nomadic or semi-nomadic groups who took advantage of the environment around the water sources inside the caves. These points formed veritable oases, surrounded by extensive grassland meadows. We know that these early groups showed respect for their dead because they deposited them inside caves as a form of veneration. Other individuals met their tragic end there when they got lost or suffered an accident. To date, 10 pre-Mayan or prehistoric human skeletons have been studied, which have been baptized as "The Woman of Naharon", "The Lady of Las Palmas", "The Man of the Temple", "The Grandfather of Muknal", "The Man of Chan Hol 1", "The Young Man of Chan Hol 2", "The Man of Pit 1", "The Man of Pit 2", "Naia" and "Ixchel". Among all the individuals studied from the caves, La Mujer de Las Palmas stands out, since the evidence points to its placement corresponding to one of the oldest funerary treatments in Mexico. Its skeleton was found fully articulated in a flexed position, at the foot of a rock that we suppose was selected inside the cave. Its preservation is extraordinary, as even the smallest bones were found, such as the ossicles of the ear or throat, as well as the fingers and toes. Such a position denotes an intention in its placement and the use, most likely, of a bundle or funerary bundle, through the use of some skin that has decomposed, as well as tendons and ropes to preserve its body from scavengers that entered the caves, such as saber-toothed tigers. She was 1.52m tall, weighed 58kg and was between 44 and 50 years old at the time of her death. As for the skeletons or fossils of animals that have been found in the caves, they correspond to large species that also lived in jungles and forests, such as gomphotheres (pachyderms), giant sloths (megatherians), giant armadillos (glyptodonts), as well as bats and tapirs larger than today, and camels. The American horse, as small as ponies, also lived here, as well as other small animals such as peccaries and foxes. So far we know the location of more than 40 skeletons corresponding to 15 species of extinct mammals in 23 submerged caves. Most of them are still there. In the records made, anatomically articulated specimens can be distinguished that show that they died in the same place where they were found. There are also concentrations of bones that could be evidence of the consumption of fauna by humans, which has already been corroborated in the remains of a peccary. The great richness of animal species extinct and prehistoric human groups at the end of the Pleistocene, allows us to consider the two largest underground rivers in the world: Ox Bel Ha and Sac Actun, as an important paleontological and prehistoric, site.

Date Range: 13000 BCE - 8000 BCE

Region: Tulum, México

Region tags: Latin America and the Caribbean

The Yucatan Peninsula is a limestone platform whose karst relief has a high permeability that favors the

vertical erosion of the limestone rock caused by slightly acidic rains (carbonic acid). This process favored the formation of the complex system of caverns, grottoes, cenotes and underground corridors, during the Late Pleistocene, when sea levels were very low. The municipality of Tulum is home to the two largest submerged caves in the world: Oxbel Ha, 235 km long, and Sak Aktun-Dos Ojos, 297 km long. At the end of the Pleistocene these caves were dry, because the sea level was up to 65m below the current level. This allowed them to be used by Paleoamerican groups for several millennia.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Current Research of the Pleistocene
- Source 2: Simposio Hombre Temprano en America
- Source 3: Human Oddiesey

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/live/epczOcb1l10?si=siDCobnZjCzRtim3>

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Notes: Underwater register and excavation

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

↳ Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Notes: Underwater excavation

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

↳ Years of excavation:

– Year range: 2000-2008

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

↳ Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Atlas Arqueológico Subacuático para el Registro, Protección y Estudio del Cenotes y Cuevas en la Península de Yucatán

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Water source

– Cave

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Is there an established route of travel connecting it to a wider transportation network:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Is it a cenotaph:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: Funerary rituals

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

↳ For the worship of a deified human:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Are grave goods present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: 5

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: 1000 years

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Are material offerings present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Are festivals present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned

with material wealth.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Yucatan Peninsula, Mexico

Bibliography

General References

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